

Methodology of evaluating the activation energy of oxygen reduction reaction on Pt-based electrodes

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ABSTRACT

Proton-exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs) operating at low (LT-PEMFC) and high temperatures (HT-PEMFC) both face the challenge of slow kinetics of the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) at the cathode. While HT-PEMFCs offer advantages such as better heat management, lower hydrogen purity requirements, and easier water management, their operation at elevated temperatures (160–200 °C) introduces difficulties due to the presence of concentrated H₃PO₄. This study presents a methodology for determining the activation energy (E^{\ddagger}) of ORR. Determination of the kinetic parameters requires correct assessment of equilibrium potential of ORR (E_{ORR}). The value of the E_{ORR} is generally influenced by the activity of the reactants and products, as well as by the temperature. A discussion of the appropriate standard states of the components is also necessary. Using linear sweep voltammetry (LSV), the exchange current density (j_{ex}) and Tafel slope were determined on a rotating electrode. The methodology was first validated on data obtained using Pt rotating disk electrode (RDE) in 0.1 M HClO₄ at temperatures from 5 to 60 °C. Then, it was applied also on a more complex HT-PEMFCs-relevant environment of 98 wt% H₃PO₄ at elevated temperatures (120–180 °C) and a limitation of using of this methodology in this system was discussed. The developed methodology offers a more accurate calculation of E^{\ddagger} and provides a general framework applicable to any electrochemical reaction where specific information about reaction mechanism, reactants and products concentrations as well as RDS are known.

List of symbols

A	Pre-exponential factor in Arrhenius equation	Various units
$a_{\text{H}^+, \text{aq}}$	activity of solvated H ⁺	1
$a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{g}}$	activity of gaseous H ₂ O	1
$a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{l}}$	activity of liquid H ₂ O	1
$a_{\text{O}_2, \text{l}}$	activity of dissolved O ₂	1
$a_{\text{O}_2, \text{g}}$	activity of gaseous O ₂	1
a_{OOH^+}	activity of adsorbed OOH ⁺	1
a_{OH^+}	activity of adsorbed OH ⁺	1
$a_{\text{Ⓢ}}$	activity of free adsorption site	1
$c_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	molar concentration of H ₂ O	mol m ⁻³
c_{H^+}	molar concentration of H ⁺	mol m ⁻³
c_{O_2}	molar concentration of O ₂	mol m ⁻³
c_{Ox}^{S}	molar concentration of oxidised species close to eld. surface	mol m ⁻³

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$c_{\text{Red}}^{\text{S}}$	molar concentration of reduced species close to eld. surface	mol m ⁻³
c_{OOH^+}	surface molar concentration of OOH ⁺	mol m ⁻²
c_{OH^+}	surface molar concentration of OH ⁺	mol m ⁻²
c_{st}^{S}	standard surface molar concentration (1)	mol m ⁻²
$c_{\text{Ⓢ}}$	surface molar concentration of free adsorption sites	mol m ⁻²
c_{st}	standard molar concentration (1000)	mol m ⁻³
D_{O_2}	diffusion coefficient of O ₂	m ² s ⁻¹
E^{\ddagger}	activation energy	J mol ⁻¹
E	electrode potential	V vs. RHE
E°	formal potential	V vs. RHE
E_T°	standard redox potential at given T	V vs. RHE
$E_{\text{ORR}, T}$	equilibrium potential of ORR at given T	V vs. RHE
$E_{\text{ORR}, T}^{\circ}$	standard redox potential of ORR at given T	V vs. RHE
$E_{\text{ORR}, \text{l}, T}^{\circ}$	standard redox potential of ORR, liquid H ₂ O as product	V vs. RHE
$E_{\text{ORR}, \text{g}, T}^{\circ}$	standard redox potential of ORR, gaseous H ₂ O as product	V vs. RHE

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Abbreviations: FC, Fuel cell; GC, Glassy carbon; HT, High temperature; LSV, Linear sweep voltammetry; MSE, Mercury-mercurous sulphate electrode; ORR, Oxygen reduction reaction; PBI, Polybenzimidazole; PEMFC, Proton-exchange membrane fuel cell; PEEK, Polyether ether ketone; PTFE, Polytetrafluorethylene; RDS, Rate-determining step; RHE, Reversible hydrogen electrode; RRE, Rotating rod disk electrode; RDE, Rotating disk electrode.

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$E_{\text{ORR},T}^{\circ}$	formal potential of ORR	V vs. RHE
f	correction factor for geometry of RRE versus RDE (1.25)	1
F	Faraday's constant (96 485)	C mol ⁻¹
ΔG_r°	standard molar Gibbs energy of reaction	J mol ⁻¹
$\Delta G_{\text{as}}^{\ddagger}$	Gibbs energy of activation calculated from $\tilde{k}_{\text{as}}^{\circ}$	J mol ⁻¹
$\Delta G_{\text{dis}}^{\ddagger}$	Gibbs energy of activation calculated from $\tilde{k}_{\text{dis}}^{\circ}$	J mol ⁻¹
$\Delta G_{j_{\text{ex}}}^{\ddagger}$	Gibbs energy of activation calculated from j_{ex}	J mol ⁻¹
$\Delta G_{j_k}^{\ddagger}$	apparent Gibbs energy of activation calculated from j_k	J mol ⁻¹
ΔG^{\ddagger}	Gibbs energy of activation	J mol ⁻¹
j	geometric current density	A m ⁻²
j_{lim}	limiting current density	A m ⁻²
j_k	kinetic current density	A m ⁻²
j_{RDS}	current density of rate determining step	A m ⁻²
j_{ex}	exchange current density	A m ⁻²
j_{red}	partial reduction current density	A m ⁻²
j_{ox}	partial oxidation current density	A m ⁻²
k	reaction rate constant	Various units
k_{eff}	effective reaction rate constant	Various units
k_{RDS}	reaction rate constant of rate determining step	Various units
k°	standard reaction rate constant	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹
$\tilde{k}_{\text{dis}}^{\circ}$	st. reaction rate constant of ORR in dissociative mechanism	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹
$\tilde{k}_{\text{as}}^{\circ}$	st. reaction rate constant of ORR in associative mechanism	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹
\overleftarrow{k}	reaction rate constant in oxidation direction	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹
\overrightarrow{k}	reaction rate constant in reduction direction	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹
\tilde{k}°	parameter proportional to k°	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹
K_x	equilibrium constant of O ₂ adsorption	1
n	number of exchanged electrons	1
ΔS_r°	standard molar entropy of reaction	J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
p_{st}	standard pressure (101 325)	Pa
$p_{\text{H}_2\text{O},T}^{\circ}$	vapour pressure of pure liquid H ₂ O at T	Pa
$p_{\text{H}_2\text{O},T}$	vapour pressure of H ₂ O at T	Pa
$p_{\text{O}_2,T}$	partial pressure of O ₂ at T	Pa
R	universal gas constant (8.314)	J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
R^2	coefficient of determination	1
T	thermodynamic temperature	K
t	temperature	°C
$x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	molar ratio of H ₂ O	1
α	charge transfer coefficient of reduction	1
β	symmetry factor	1
$\gamma_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	activity coefficient of H ₂ O	1
γ_{O_2}	activity coefficient of O ₂	1
γ_{H^+}	activity coefficient of H ⁺	1
$\gamma_{\text{OOH}^{\ast}}$	activity coefficient of adsorbed OOH [†]	1
$\gamma_{\text{OH}^{\ast}}$	activity coefficient of adsorbed OH [†]	1
$\gamma_{\text{⊖}}$	activity coefficient of free adsorption site	1
η	overpotential	V
ν	kinematic viscosity	m ² s ⁻¹
φ_{O_2}	fugacity coefficient of O ₂	1
$\varphi_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	fugacity coefficient of H ₂ O	1
ω	angular velocity	rad s ⁻¹

1. Introduction

Low-temperature proton-exchange membrane fuel cells (LT-PEMFCs) and high-temperature proton-exchange membrane fuel cells (HT-PEMFCs) are two distinct types of fuel cells that have attracted significant attention for their respective applications in clean energy production from hydrogen. While LT-PEMFCs typically operate at temperatures of 50–80 °C, HT-PEMFCs function in higher temperature range of 160–200 °C, offering several advantages, such as better heat recovery, simplified water management, and greater tolerance to impure H₂, including resistance to CO poisoning at concentrations of up to 3 vol% [1–3]. Since HT-PEMFCs are operated at temperatures above 100 °C [4], polybenzimidazole (PBI) doped with high concentration of H₃PO₄ is widely used as PEM [5–8]. In both LT-PEMFCs and HT-PEMFCs, catalyst is typically based on Pt metals or their alloys [9–12]. Despite these

differences, both systems share some common challenges. For an energy efficient operation of a FC, it is essential to maximise the rates of kinetics of electrode reactions, i.e. to minimise the polarisation overvoltage. It is usually the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR), taking place in the cathode catalyst layer, which is responsible for the most significant activation losses. ORR has slower kinetics compared to the H₂ oxidation reaction taking place at the anode side and limits the whole process [13–15]. One of the parameters that determine the rate of the electrode reaction is the exchange current density, j_{ex} , i.e. the absolute value of partial current density at the equilibrium potential of ORR, E_{ORR} (a higher j_{ex} value corresponds to a faster kinetics of the ORR at E_{ORR}). The activation energy (E^{\ddagger}) of ORR can play a crucial role in determining the overall FC efficiency [16]. However, determining accurate values for E_{ORR} and j_{ex} can be complicated by the dependence of these quantities on temperature and the activities of reactants and products, which differ significantly between the two PEMFC systems. For example, while the role of H₃PO₄ on the activity and concentrations of H₂O, H⁺, or O₂ in HT-PEMFCs introduces severe complications, analogous values in H₂O-based systems corresponding to LT-PEMFCs operation are relatively simple to assess. Therefore, in the context of HT-PEMFC, it is especially problematic to determine the E_{ORR} of an ORR half-reaction [17–19]. The literature is inconsistent in the approach to treat the problem and often ignores an influence of reactant/product activities in H₃PO₄ [12,20–25] on resulting E_{ORR} (while considering change of the standard redox potential value E_{ORR}° with temperature) and sometimes even uses E_{ORR} value valid at 25 °C, i.e. ($E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ} = 1.229 \text{ V}$) [9,26–29] as an equilibrium potential E_{ORR} at higher temperatures. This necessarily leads to incorrect j_{ex} values. Moreover, as will be shown below, even knowledge of j_{ex} values at various temperatures is not sufficient for correct calculation of E^{\ddagger} .

The dependence between reaction rate constant k and E^{\ddagger} or in this case Gibbs energy of activation (ΔG^{\ddagger}) is given by the Arrhenius equation, Eq. (1)

$$k = A e^{\frac{-\Delta G^{\ddagger}}{RT}} \quad (1)$$

where A represents pre-exponential factor, R universal gas constant and T thermodynamical temperature. In the case of elementary electrochemical reaction ($\text{Ox} + n e^{-} \rightleftharpoons \text{Red}$), the current density j can be calculated from the values of the rate constants of backward (oxidation) and forward (reduction) reaction \overleftarrow{k} and \overrightarrow{k} , respectively, according to Eq. (2):

$$j = nF \left(\overleftarrow{k} c_{\text{Red}}^{\text{S}} e^{\frac{(1-\beta)F\eta}{RT}} - \overrightarrow{k} c_{\text{Ox}}^{\text{S}} e^{\frac{-\beta F\eta}{RT}} \right) \quad (2)$$

where n represents number of exchanged electrons (in case of elementary reaction, generally $n = 1$), F is Faraday constant, $c_{\text{Red/Ox}}^{\text{S}}$ represent concentrations (close to electrode surface) of the reduced and oxidised specie involved in the redox reaction, β is symmetry factor and η represents overpotential. However, situation in the case of ORR is significantly more complex since ORR is far from being an elementary reaction. Moreover, it involves several adsorbed intermediates. Therefore, finding dependence between system composition and j or j_{ex} and in turn between j_{ex} and k becomes more complicated.

This paper presents a methodology for calculating E_{ORR} and ΔG^{\ddagger} . At first, the methodology is verified using ORR data obtained using Pt rotating disk electrode (RDE) in aqueous 0.1 M HClO₄. These measurements are conducted over a temperature range of 5–60 °C, where thermodynamic data (activities of products and reactants, their temperature dependence) are more easily accessible, allowing for a more straightforward analysis of j_{ex} and the determination of ΔG^{\ddagger} . The validated methodology is then applied to the more complex environment of conc. H₃PO₄, using thin-film of Pt/C on rotating rod disk electrode (RRE) operating at temperatures between 120 and 180 °C.

2. Experimental

2.1. Used chemicals and materials

The commercially available catalyst HiSPEC4000 (40 wt% Pt on carbon black) (Johnson-Matthey, UK) was used as the investigated Pt/C catalyst. The following chemicals were also used in the work: 85 wt% H₃PO₄ (extra pure, Acros Organics), 30 wt% H₂O₂ (per analysis, non-stabilised, Lach-Ner), *N,N*-dimethylformamide (per analysis, Penta), 70 wt% HClO₄ (per analysis or Supra-Qualität, Roth ROTIPURAN®), 96 wt% H₂SO₄ (per analysis, Penta). 10 wt% solution of polybenzimidazole in *N,N*-dimethylformamide (PBI Performance products), O₂ (99.5 %, SIAD), H₂ (99.95 %, SIAD) and N₂ (99.99 %, SIAD). Demineralised water (conductivity <0.5 μS cm⁻¹) used during the work was prepared by DIWA 3rica system (WATEK, Czechia).

H₂O₂ was used for purification of commercial H₃PO₄ [30,31] from H₃PO₃ which is electrochemically active in the ORR potential region [32]. The 85 wt% H₃PO₄ was mixed with the 30 wt% H₂O₂ in volumetric ratio of 2:1. The mixture was poured in a PTFE beaker, heated to 160 °C and left at this temperature for 24 h. Prepared H₃PO₄ was poured in a glass storage bottle while still hot. The concentration of thus purified H₃PO₄ was then determined by acid-base titration. Titration was performed using automatic titrator, (Easy Pro, Mettler Toledo), with 0.1 M NaOH (Standard solution, Penta) serving as a titration agent. The concentration of H₃PO₄ was 97.6 ± 0.6 wt% (i.e., 70.9 ± 0.4 wt% P₄O₁₀), which also corresponds to the observed density (1.849 ± 0.006 g cm⁻³), in accordance with the literature [33,34]. Thus prepared H₃PO₄ was used for all measurements.

2.2. Set-up for measurements in 0.1 M HClO₄ at temperature 5–65 °C

Measurements were performed in a glass electrochemical cell (100 cm³). The measuring cell (including the bubblers) was cleaned prior to use by triple rinsing with peroxysulfuric acid (Piranha solution, prepared by mixing 3 parts of 96 wt% H₂SO₄ with 1 part of 30 wt% H₂O₂) and, after rinsing with deionized H₂O, the cell was filled with deionized H₂O and left for 1 h. Subsequently, it was dried at room temperature. The electrolyte was 0.1 mol dm⁻³ HClO₄, the temperature was maintained using a thermostat (F12, Julabo, Germany). Measurements were performed on a potentiostat (PGSTAT302N, Autolab Metrohm, Switzerland), electrode revolution was controlled by a rotor (MCUR71221, Metrohm, Switzerland). A three-electrode setup was used; the counter electrode was a Pt wire of about 16 mm² placed in a glass tube separated from the main compartment of the electrolyte by a porous frit; the reference electrode was fresh RHE (Hydroflex, Gaskatel GmbH, Germany), placed directly into the electrolyte solution. The working electrode was a 3 mm diameter Pt rotating disk electrode (RDE) with PEEK insulation (Metrohm, Switzerland). The RDE was immersed approximately 5 mm below the electrolyte level.

For each temperature, Pt RDE was first cycled 20 times within the potential range of 0 to 1.65 V vs. RHE at a sweep rate of 100 mV s⁻¹ in the N₂ saturated electrolyte before the LSV measurement. Subsequently, the LSVs were measured (starts with one cleaning CV in the potential range of 0.01 V to 1.65 V and back to 0.01 V vs. RHE at a sweep rate of 100 mV s⁻¹, then one LSV in the potential range of 0.01 V to 1.65 V vs. RHE) at 10 mV s⁻¹ in the N₂ saturated electrolyte at revolving RDE (900 rpm). These currents were subtracted from the currents obtained in the O₂ saturated electrolyte by same protocol. All experimental voltammograms were recorded using active IR compensation. The Savitzky-Golay filter (cubic, frame length 9 points) was used to process the measured data. To ensure reproducible results, each measurement was performed in triplicate. The temperature was varied from 5 to 60 °C, in increments of 5 °C (a total of 12 temperatures). Between each temperature change, the protocol was repeated (including the initial CVs), and the electrolyte saturation with O₂/N₂ was maintained for a minimum of 15 min.

The pH of 0.1 M HClO₄ solution in the glass cell in the studied

temperature range was measured separately (without N₂ or O₂ saturation). pH was determined with a titrator (HI932, Hanna Instruments, USA) using a glass electrode (HI1131, Hanna Instruments, USA), and a thermocouple (HI7662-TW, Hanna Instruments, USA) for temperature compensation. Calibration was performed using buffers at pH 4.01 and 7.01 (Hanna Instruments, Italy) over a temperature range of 3–65 °C, with a total of 2 × 14 calibration points.

2.3. Set-up for measurements in 97.6 wt% H₃PO₄ at temperature 120–180 °C

The measurements were carried out in a PTFE vessel (100 cm³) placed in a heating mantle (WiseTherm WHM, Witeg) heated to desired temperature and containing purified 97.6 wt% H₃PO₄ as an electrolyte. All measurements were performed with EC301 potentiostat (Stanford Research Systems, UK). A rotator with rotation control (AFMSRXE, Pine Research, USA) was used in combination with an in-house made shaft. The shaft was constructed from a CNC axis with centering and adjusted to a precise diameter on a lathe [35,36]. The temperature was controlled automatically by an in-house made temperature controller and monitored by a thermocouple (5SRTC, Omega, USA) placed in a glass tube. The counter electrode was a roll of Pt foil with an area of about 7 cm² separated from the main compartment of the electrolyte by a ceramic frit. A Hg|Hg₂SO₄ in saturated K₂SO₄ solution (MSE), 0.654 V vs. RHE (Monokrystaly, Czechia) was used as a reference electrode. It was separated from the H₃PO₄ environment by a double junction, the first one filled with 97.6 wt% H₃PO₄, the second with saturated K₂SO₄ solution. The second junction was placed in a short Liebig cooler tempered to 25 °C by a cryostat (Julabo F12). The cell was sealed with PTFE tape (DuPont).

The working electrode itself was a glassy carbon rod (Sigradur® G, HTW, Germany) of 5 mm diameter and 6 cm length. Before each ink deposition, the electrode disk was polished with a sandpaper (MicroCut P4000, Buehler, USA) and then with a suspension of alumina (0.3 μm) on felt. To prevent the ink loss from the RRE disk during catalyst application, its sides were wrapped with several layers of PTFE tape. The thin film electrodes were prepared according to the following procedure: 2.5 mg of catalyst was dispersed in 10 cm³ of acetone to achieve an overall Pt concentration of 0.1 g dm⁻³. The mixture was homogenised in an ice bath using an ultrasonic probe (Sonoplus MS73, Bandelin, Germany) for 30 min, power 12 W. To achieve final Pt loading of 10 μg cm⁻², a total of 20 mm³ of ink was applied dropwise (2 mm³ per drop) to the GC rod base using a micropipette (Eppendorf). After each drop, the surface of the disk was allowed to dry at room temperature. In order to prevent an agglomeration of catalyst in ink suspension during thin film preparation, the ink was vigorously stirred with a PTFE magnetic bar (1 cm length) at 500 rpm using stirrer (MR3004, Heidolph, Germany). Then, for immobilisation of the thin film on the surface of the electrode, 4 mm³ of PBI solution in dimethylformamide (concentration of 0.5 g dm⁻³) was applied in two drops on the surface of the thin film. The PBI solution was vigorously stirred at 500 rpm for at least 1 h before and during deposition. The prepared RREs were dried at ambient temperature and stored in a dry box under N₂. The PTFE tape was removed after final drying.

Each prepared electrode was first cycled 3 times in the potential range of 0.3 V to -0.05 vs. MSE (sweep rate 100 mV s⁻¹) in the N₂ saturated electrolyte (saturation time 30 min) at RRE electrode without the rotation. Then, after saturation of the electrolyte with O₂ (saturation time 30 min), the LSVs were measured in the potential range of 0.3 V to -0.1 V vs. MSE at a sweep rate of 5 mV s⁻¹ on RRE at various revolution rates (400, 900, 1600 and 2500 rpm). Finally, the electrolyte was re-saturated with N₂ (saturation time 30 min) and LSVs were repeated at the same settings. These measurements were then used as a background that was subtracted from the previous LSVs measured in the O₂-saturated electrolyte. All measurements were performed at various temperatures (from 120, 140, 160 to 180 °C) using the same electrode. The

potentials measured using MSE reference electrode (at each temperature) were recalculated to RHE scale. For this purpose, in-house made reversible hydrogen electrode (Pt wire coated with Pt black immersed directly in H_3PO_4 electrolyte, saturated with H_2) was used in the same setup, without the use of additional electrodes or gas saturation. Data for MSE vs. RHE were collected over the temperature range of 120–180 °C. This dependence can be approximated by the equation in Eq. (3) (R^2 value 0.975 for the temperature range of 120–180 °C),

$$E_{\text{MSE},t} = -694.6 \text{ mV} + t \cdot 0.70 \text{ mV } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1} \quad (3)$$

where t is temperature in °C.

All voltammograms were corrected for the IR drop during the measurements. The Savitzky-Golay filter (cubic, frame length 7 points) was used to smooth the measured data. To ensure reproducible results, each measurement was performed in triplicate and with at least three different working electrodes.

3. Results

3.1. Equilibrium potential of ORR

As discussed in the introduction, for determination of j_{ex} values at given temperature T (and consequently the ΔG^\ddagger), it is necessary to correctly determine corresponding $E_{\text{ORR},T}$, which requires knowledge of standard redox potential of ORR ($E_{\text{ORR},T}^\circ$) and the activities of the involved components at given conditions [21,22].

In LT-PEMFC, it is most natural to consider the formation of a liquid H_2O , consequently the overall process can be written by Eq. (4). In HT-PEMFC, which operates above 100 °C, it is not obvious at first sight whether H_2O is formed in the liquid phase (due to presence of H_3PO_4 phase), see Eq. (4), or in the gaseous phase (Eq. (5)).

The corresponding ORR processes at the cathode are described by Eq. (6) and Eq. (7).

$E_{\text{ORR},T}^\circ$ of the reactions Eq. (6) and Eq. (7) can be calculated from the respective standard reaction Gibbs energies at given T , i.e. $\Delta G_{r,l,T}^\circ$ and $\Delta G_{r,g,T}^\circ$ according to Eq. (8) [37].

$$E_{\text{ORR},T}^\circ = \frac{-\Delta G_{r,T}^\circ}{nF} \quad (8)$$

For a reaction considering the formation of liquid and gaseous H_2O at 25 °C (298 K), $E_{\text{ORR},l,298}^\circ = 1.229 \text{ V}$ vs RHE and the $E_{\text{ORR},g,298}^\circ = 1.184 \text{ V}$, respectively, using thermodynamic data [24]. Temperature dependence of $E_{\text{ORR},T}^\circ$ (at constant pressure of $p_{\text{st.}} = 101\,325 \text{ Pa}$) can be calculated using Eq. (9) [19,37,38],

$$E_{\text{ORR},l/g,T}^\circ = E_{\text{ORR},298}^\circ + \frac{-\Delta S_{r,l/g}^\circ}{nF} \cdot (T - 298) \quad (9)$$

where ΔS_r° represents standard molar entropy of the reaction (Eqs. (6) and (7)), its value is $-326.7 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for $\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{l})$ as a product of ORR and $-88.9 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for $\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{g})$; corresponding slopes $dE_{\text{ORR},T}^\circ/dT$ for $\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{l})$ and $\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{g})$ are $-0.8465 \text{ mV K}^{-1}$ and $-0.2302 \text{ mV K}^{-1}$, respectively.

The derivation of $E_{\text{ORR},l/g,T}^\circ$ is thoroughly discussed in SI (section S1)

Fig. 1. Standard redox (dash-dotted) (E_{ORR}°) and equilibrium (E_{ORR}) potentials (solid lines and triangles) for ORR. Triangles denote E_{ORR} values in 0.1 M HClO_4 at temperatures of 5–60 °C for liquid H_2O as a product, solid lines denote E_{ORR} values 97.6 wt% H_3PO_4 at temperatures of 120–180 °C for liquid (blue) or gaseous (red) H_2O as a product. E_{ORR} values were calculated using E_{ORR}° provided in Tables S1 and S2 and activities of components summarised in Tables S1 and S2. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

and resulting values of $E_{\text{ORR},l/g,T}^\circ$ are summarised in Tables S1 and S2. Fig. 1 graphically summarises the E_{ORR}° for region of interest 5–180 °C and 120–180 °C respectively.

To sum up, if the $E_{\text{ORR},l,T}^\circ$ and $E_{\text{ORR},g,T}^\circ$ values are compared, it is clear that at 100 °C (at standard pressure) the potentials are identical since chemical potentials of the liquid and gaseous H_2O at boiling point are equal.

Using the Nernst equation and taking into account activities of the reacting components and products presented in section S1 in SI, it is possible to calculate the $E_{\text{ORR},l/g,T}$ for ORR yielding liquid H_2O in 0.1 M HClO_4 (Eq. (6)) and for ORRs yielding both liquid and gaseous H_2O (Eq. (6) and Eq. (7)) in 97.6 wt% H_3PO_4 . In the second case, the resulting value of $E_{\text{ORR},T}$ will be the same for a given temperature for both the reactions written in the notation Eq. (6) (with $\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{l})$ as a product) and the reaction written in Eq. (7) (with $\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{g})$ as a product). The calculated $E_{\text{ORR},T}$ values for 0.1 M HClO_4 at 5–65 °C and for 97.6 wt% H_3PO_4 at 120–180 °C are summarised in Table S5 and Table S6 in SI, respectively, as well as in Fig. 1.

As already mentioned, in HT-PEMFC it may not be obvious if H_2O is formed in the liquid or in the gaseous phase. Due to equilibrium between the two, it is obvious that it does not matter which of the two options is chosen as long as appropriate thermodynamic treatment and data for activities of involved components are used. Indeed, the calculated $E_{\text{ORR},g,T}$ and $E_{\text{ORR},l,T}$ potentials vary by less than 1 % (in order of mV) over a wide range of temperatures. This is given by minor error in the literature thermodynamic data. Nevertheless, in the following chapters, the value of $E_{\text{ORR},g,T}$ will be used preferentially because liquid-vapour equilibria for H_3PO_4 are much more covered in the literature than data required for calculation of the $a_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}$ in H_3PO_4 .

3.2. Evaluation of ORR curves obtained in 0.1 M HClO_4 at temperature 5–60 °C

Polarisation curves measured in 0.1 M HClO_4 at temperatures of

Fig. 2. LSVs measured at Pt-RDE using revolution rates 900 rpm; 0.1 M HClO₄, 10 mV s⁻¹, temperatures of 5–55 °C, corrected for background currents and uncompensated resistance, use of corresponding $E_{ORR,I,T}$.

5–55 °C are presented in Fig. 2.

According to Koutecky-Levich equation (Eq. (10)), the measured current density j is affected by the kinetic current density j_k and limiting current density j_{lim} ,

$$\frac{1}{j} = \frac{1}{j_{lim}} + \frac{1}{j_k} \quad (10)$$

With the knowledge of j and j_{lim} , the values of j_k can then be calculated from Eq. (10). After plotting the decadic logarithms of the j_k values over the investigated potential range, Tafel plots are obtained, see Figs. S1–S12 in SI. The results of Tafel slope fitting, i.e. low-overpotential Tafel slopes (with corresponding charge transfer coefficients of reduction (α) and exchange current densities j_{ex} are summarised in Table 1.

It can be seen that the Tafel slope increases with increasing temperature (this is consistent with [39–43]) and reaches a value of 124 mV dec⁻¹ at 25 °C in 0.1 M HClO₄, which is in agreement with the literature [44–46]. As can be seen, the temperature dependence of the Tafel slope is consistent with theoretical predictions (ideally around 0.40 mV dec⁻¹ K⁻¹ corresponding to $\alpha \approx 0.5$). An observed average value is approximately 0.53 mV dec⁻¹ K⁻¹ over the entire temperature range. Because $\alpha \approx 0.5$, it can be assumed that the first electron transfer reaction represents a rate-determining step (RDS) in the whole ORR process (consistent with literature [47–49]).

Table 1

Summary of ORR kinetic parameters determined from Tafel plots at temperatures of 5–60 °C, LSVs measured at Pt-RDE using revolution rates 900 rpm; 0.1 M HClO₄, 10 mV s⁻¹, corrected for background currents and uncompensated resistance, use of corresponding $E_{ORR,I,T}$.

$t/^\circ\text{C}$	Tafel slope / mV dec ⁻¹	α	$j_{ex} / \text{mA m}^{-2}$
5	118	0.469	0.71
10	119	0.473	0.92
15	121	0.471	1.27
20	122	0.476	1.78
25	124	0.475	2.21
30	125	0.483	2.59
35	127	0.480	3.12
40	127	0.489	3.66
45	133	0.474	4.61
50	137	0.466	6.33
55	144	0.453	7.89
60	151	0.437	11.2

Fig. 3. Arrhenius plots from j_k at various overpotentials (100–800 mV vs. $E_{ORR,I,T}$) at temperatures of 5–60 °C, LSVs measured at Pt-RDE using revolution rates 900 rpm; 0.1 M HClO₄, 10 mV s⁻¹, corrected for background currents and uncompensated resistance, use of corresponding $E_{ORR,I,T}$.

It can also be seen that the j_{ex} values increase with temperature. From these values ($\Delta G_{j_{ex}}^\ddagger$) will subsequently be derived. Sometimes, j_k values at given overpotential are (inappropriately) used to construct Arrhenius plot [50–52], i.e. $\log j_k$ vs $1/T$. This is shown in Fig. 3, where such “Arrhenius plots“ for overpotentials of 100–800 mV vs. E_{ORR} are presented. It is evident that not all the j_k values increase with temperature, therefore, this analysis cannot yield linear Arrhenius dependence and subsequently “ $\Delta G_{j_k}^\ddagger$ “. In the region of low current densities (low overpotentials), it is generally evident that the uncertainty introduced by background current subtraction, noise, and other effects is too large. On the other hand, in (and close to) the potential region where limiting current densities are observed, the error of mass transport correction introduced by Koutecky-Levich equation application becomes too large. For this reason, middle overpotential potential region is typically used for Arrhenius plot analysis.

3.3. Reaction rate constant - mechanisms of the reaction

In order to correctly determine the value of ΔG^\ddagger from Arrhenius type equation, it is necessary to find, how an effective reaction rate constant value of the whole the reaction sequence, k_{eff} , changes with temperature. To do that, the relation between j_{ex} and other parameters including concentration of the reactants/products and reaction mechanism, i.e. $j_{ex} = f(k_{eff}, c_{H^+}, c_{O_2}, c_{H_2O}, \text{mechanism})$ has to be determined. Considering that the reaction mechanism consists of series of elementary steps, the particular form of the dependence is influenced by both, the order and rates of individual elementary reactions. An analytical expression for $j_{ex} = f(k_{RDS}, c_{H^+}, c_{O_2}, c_{H_2O}, \text{mechanism})$ dependence can be easily derived if a so-called rate-determining step RDS with k_{RDS} exists (and its stoichiometry is known) in the reaction sequence. In the particular case of ORR, the overall reaction is a 4 e⁻ reduction process leading to H₂O (Eq. (6) or Eq. (7)). For the mathematical description of the rate of the whole reaction sequence, it is important to consider:

- pseudo-equilibrium of the reaction(s) preceding the RDS
- rate of the RDS
- pseudo-equilibrium of the reaction(s) following the RDS

Most authors assume that the mechanism of the ORR process begins with a chemical adsorption of O₂ on the surface of Pt. Depending on

whether O_2 dissociates upon adsorption or not, two different ORR mechanisms can be distinguished, an associative or a dissociative one. The dissociative path is treated in section S4, Eqs. (S9)–(S25). When the associative path of the ORR is considered to take place, the overall reaction is (Eq. (11)):

The adsorption of O_2 leads to O_2^* adsorbed on the Pt surface (Eq. (12)).

Subsequently, this adsorbed O_2^* undergoes one-electron reduction to adsorbed OOH^* (Eq. (13)).

The index “as” was introduced to indicate that it relates to the associative O_2 adsorption pathway. The literature suggests that this step represents the RDS [7,14,19,53]. This is also in agreement with our data showing that $\alpha \approx 0.5$. Therefore, it can be considered that experimentally determined α value corresponds to the value of the symmetry factor, β , of the first electron transfer reaction, i.e. Eq. (13). Further one-electron reductions and/or chemical steps follow. However, all the reactions following the RDS can be assumed to proceed near equilibrium conditions, so it does not really matter what is exact mechanism of the remaining part of ORR process and it is sufficient to consider only the overall post-RDS reaction, see Eq. (14).

The overall current density is proportional to the current density of the RDS (Eq. 13), j_{RDS} , as expressed by the kinetic equation (Eq. (15))

$$j = 4j_{\text{RDS}} = 4F \overleftarrow{k}_{as} c_{\text{OOH}^*} e^{\frac{(1-\beta)F(E-E_2^*)}{RT}} - 4F \overrightarrow{k}_{as} c_{O_2^*} c_{H^+} e^{\frac{-\beta F(E-E_2^*)}{RT}} \quad (15)$$

where E_2^* is formal potential of the RDS, i.e. Eq. (13) and c_x^* represent surface concentrations of individual adsorbed species. Chemical equilibrium in step preceding the RDS (Eq. (12)) can be described by Eq. (16),

$$K_1 = \frac{a_{O_2^*}}{a_{O_2} a_{\textcircled{\ominus}}} = \frac{\gamma_{O_2^*} c_{O_2^*}^* c_{\text{st.}}^* c_{\text{st.}}^*}{\gamma_{O_2} c_{O_2} \gamma_{\textcircled{\ominus}} c_{\text{st.}}^* c_{\text{st.}}^*} = \frac{\gamma_{O_2^*}}{\gamma_{O_2} \gamma_{\textcircled{\ominus}}} K_1' \quad (16)$$

and when considering activity coefficients $\gamma_x = 1$, $c_{O_2^*}^*$ can be expressed using Eq. 17,

$$c_{O_2^*}^* = \frac{K_1' c_{O_2} c_{\textcircled{\ominus}}}{c_{\text{st.}}} \quad (17)$$

where K_1' is apparent equilibrium constant (dimensionless), $c_{\textcircled{\ominus}}$ represents molar surface concentration of free adsorption sites, the standard molar concentration ($c_{\text{st.}} = 1000 \text{ mol m}^{-3}$) and $c_{\text{st.}}^*$ ($=1 \text{ mol m}^{-2}$) is the standard surface concentration. Analogously, the derivation of the c_{OOH^*} is based on assuming pseudo-equilibrium in the overall remaining reaction after the RDS, i.e. Eq. (14), by means of Nernst equation (Eq. (18)).

$$E_3 = E_3^\circ - \frac{RT}{3F} \ln \left(\frac{a_{H_2O}^2 a_{\textcircled{\ominus}}}{a_{H^+}^3 a_{\text{OOH}^*}} \right) \quad (18)$$

Rearrangement provides the desired result, see Eq. (19). The standard state used for the adsorbed species is based on recommendations provided in [54].

$$E_3 = E_3^\circ - \frac{RT}{3F} \ln \left(\frac{x_{H_2O,l}^2 \frac{c_{\textcircled{\ominus}}}{c_{\text{st.}}^*}}{\frac{c_{H^+}^3 c_{\text{OOH}^*}}{c_{\text{st.}}^* c_{\text{st.}}^*}} \right) - \frac{RT}{3F} \ln \left(\frac{\gamma_{H_2O,l}^2 \gamma_{\textcircled{\ominus}}}{\gamma_{H^+}^3 \gamma_{\text{OOH}^*}} \right)$$

$$E_3 = E_3^\circ - \frac{RT}{3F} \ln \left(\frac{x_{H_2O,l}^2 \frac{c_{\textcircled{\ominus}}}{c_{\text{st.}}^*}}{\frac{c_{H^+}^3 c_{\text{OOH}^*}}{c_{\text{st.}}^* c_{\text{st.}}^*}} \right)$$

$$c_{\text{OOH}^*} = \frac{x_{H_2O,l}^2 c_{\text{st.}}^* c_{\textcircled{\ominus}}}{c_{H^+}^3} e^{\frac{3F(E_3 - E_3^\circ)}{RT}} \quad (19)$$

After substituting the relations Eq. (16) and Eq. (19) into Eq. (15), the overall kinetic equation Eq. (20) of the overall reaction (Eq. (11)) is obtained.

$$j = 4F \overleftarrow{k}_{as} \frac{x_{H_2O,l}^2 c_{\text{st.}}^* c_{\textcircled{\ominus}}}{c_{H^+}^3} e^{\frac{3F(E_3 - E_3^\circ)}{RT}} e^{\frac{(1-\beta)F(E-E_2^*)}{RT}} - 4F \overrightarrow{k}_{as} \frac{K_1' c_{O_2} c_{\textcircled{\ominus}} c_{H^+}}{c_{\text{st.}}} e^{\frac{-\beta F(E-E_2^*)}{RT}} \quad (20)$$

Since the reference potential in Eq. (15) is the formal potential E_2^* of the step in Eq. (13), it applies that $\overleftarrow{k}_{as} = \overrightarrow{k}_{as} = k_{as}^\circ$. If it is moreover considered that step in Eq. (13) represents the RDS, it becomes obvious that this k_{as}° value should be used in determining ΔG^\ddagger of the whole ORR process, i.e. the purpose of following derivations is to find dependence $k_{as}^\circ = f(j_{\text{ex}}, c_{H^+}, c_{O_2}, x_{H_2O})$ for the given reaction mechanism.

Having analytical expression for the current density of the overall ORR process (Eq. (20)) allows to investigate also the corresponding exchange current density, j_{ex} . This can be done by setting the electrode potential E equal to E_{ORR} as defined by Nernst equation for overall ORR process (Eq. S1). This corresponds to state with $j = 0$ and consequently $j_{\text{ex}} = -j_{\text{red}} = j_{\text{ox}}$, where j_{ox} and j_{red} correspond to the first and second term on the right side of the Eq. (20) (and are usually called partial oxidation and partial reduction current density), respectively. Further operations with j_{red} are presented below, see Eqs. (21)–(22). Corresponding treatment of j_{ox} is summarised in S3 see Eqs. S7–S8.

$$-j_{\text{ex}} = j_{\text{red}} = -4F k_{as}^\circ K_1' c_{O_2} c_{\textcircled{\ominus}} c_{\text{st.}}^{-2} c_{H^+} e^{\frac{-\beta F \left(\frac{-RT}{4F} \ln \frac{x_{H_2O,l}^2 c_{\text{st.}}^* c_{\textcircled{\ominus}}}{c_{O_2} c_{H^+}^4 \frac{c_{\text{st.}}^* c_{\text{st.}}^*}{c_{\text{st.}}^* c_{\text{st.}}^*} + (E_{\text{ORR}}^\circ - E_2^*) \right)}{RT}} \quad (21)$$

After rearrangement, the Eq. (22) is obtained.

$$-j_{\text{ex}} = j_{\text{red}} = -4F k_{as}^\circ c_{H^+}^{1-\beta} c_{O_2}^{1-\frac{\beta}{4}} x_{H_2O,l}^{\frac{\beta}{2}} c_{\text{st.}}^{-2+\frac{5\beta}{4}} \left\{ K_1' e^{\frac{-\beta F (E_{\text{ORR}}^\circ - E_2^*)}{RT}} \right\} \quad (22)$$

Analogously to the above treatment of j_{red} , the development of the partial oxidation current density j_{ox} , i.e. the first term on the right side of Eq. 20, yields the very same dependence of j_{ex} on composition of the system. For details, see Eqs. S7–S8 in section S3.

Considering that $c_{\textcircled{\ominus}}$ (in Eq. (22) and Eq. S8) must be the same for both partial current density notations, j_{ox} and j_{red} differ (except for the sign) only by notation of constant terms. In particular, comparison of Eq. (22) and Eq. S8 yields Eq. (23), where the differences between E_1^* (E_2^*) and E_{ORR}° and K_1' stand out.

$$e^{\frac{3F(E_{\text{ORR}}^\circ - E_3^\circ) + F(E_{\text{ORR}}^\circ - E_2^*)}{RT}} = K_1' \quad (23)$$

After taking logarithm of Eq. (23) and substituting for formal potentials E_x° and apparent rate constant K_1' , equality Eq. (24) can be obtained,

$$\begin{aligned}
-4FE_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ} &= -FE_2^{\circ} - 3FE_3^{\circ} - RT \ln K_1 \\
-4FE_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ} - RT \ln \frac{\gamma_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2}{\gamma_{\text{H}^+}^2 \gamma_{\text{O}_2}} &= -FE_2^{\circ} - 3FE_3^{\circ} - RT \ln K_1 - RT \ln \frac{\gamma_{\text{O}_2}^*}{\gamma_{\text{O}_2} \gamma_{\text{O}_2}} \\
&\quad - RT \ln \frac{\gamma_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2 \gamma_{\text{O}_2}}{\gamma_{\text{H}^+}^4 \gamma_{\text{O}_2}} \\
\Delta G_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ} &= \Delta G_2^{\circ} + \Delta G_3^{\circ} + \Delta G_1^{\circ} \quad (24)
\end{aligned}$$

which is consistent with Hess's law of the thermodynamic cycle supporting validity of the whole treatment. $\Delta G_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ}$ (or in general ΔG° of the overall process) is available in literature. Therefore, if another two Gibbs energies from Eq. (24) are known, the remaining one can easily be calculated. By excluding the mostly unknown but at given temperature constant terms (curly brackets) in Eq. (22) or Eq. S8, the desired relation between k_{as}° and experimentally determined j_{ex} value at each particular temperature is obtained, see Eq. (25). The only parameter, which is not easily available, is c_{O_2} . It is important to mention that, using Eq. (25), only relative changes of the k_{as}° denoted as $\tilde{k}_{\text{as}}^{\circ}$ could be obtained.

$$k_{\text{as}}^{\circ} \propto \tilde{k}_{\text{as}}^{\circ} = \frac{j_{\text{ex}}}{c_{\text{H}^+}^{1-\beta} c_{\text{O}_2}^{1-\frac{\beta}{4}} x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\frac{\beta}{2}} c_{\text{O}_2}} \quad (25)$$

However, if j_{ex} values are determined at various temperatures, variation of all parameters in Eq. (22) (or Eq. S8) must be considered. It is obvious that values such as c_{O_2} , K_1 and terms $(E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ} - E_2^{\circ})/RT$ (or $(E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ} - E_3^{\circ})/RT$) are not easy to obtain and one is left with simplifying assumption that their values do not vary significantly with temperature. For example, it can be assumed that because of nature of (adsorption) process, K_1 value should decrease with increasing temperature, while value of c_{O_2} should increase, so it is possible that product $c_{\text{O}_2} K_1$ (in Eq. (22)) will not change dramatically with temperature. Currently, the mechanism of the ORR is widely studied using computational methods, such as density functional theory and similar approaches [49,55–64]. Therefore, if the values of formal potentials or equilibrium constants in Eq. (23) become accessible, they could be considered within this approach.

If it is considered that the ORR process proceeds via dissociative path according to Eqs. S10, S11 and S12, the analogous treatment (see section S4) yields Eq. (26).

$$-j_{\text{ex}} = j_{\text{red}} = -4FK_{\text{dis}}^{\circ} c_{\text{H}^+}^{1-\beta} c_{\text{O}_2}^{1-\frac{\beta}{4}} x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\frac{\beta}{2}} c_{\text{O}_2}^{\frac{3-\beta}{2}} \left\{ \sqrt{K_2} e^{-\frac{\beta F(E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ} - E_4^{\circ})}{RT}} \right\} \quad (26)$$

Then, the result is the relation Eq. (27).

$$k_{\text{dis}}^{\circ} \propto \tilde{k}_{\text{dis}}^{\circ} = \frac{j_{\text{ex}}}{c_{\text{H}^+}^{1-\beta} c_{\text{O}_2}^{1-\frac{\beta}{4}} x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\frac{\beta}{2}} c_{\text{O}_2}} \quad (27)$$

It is currently unclear from the literature which ORR reaction pathway is preferred under the given conditions. Some authors mention the dissociative pathway as the preferred mechanism [65–68], but arguments can also be found for a RDS in the associative reaction followed by dissociation of the already absorbed molecular O_2 [69,70]. Last but not least, the preference of the associative pathway depends on the Pt surface coverage and the ratio of c_{O_2} to c_{O_2} [38], the type of crystal lattices [71,72] and temperature [72,73]. Finally, the analogous expression for $\tilde{k}_{\text{dis/as}}^{\circ}$ can be performed for α values corresponding to different RDS. In other words, while the derivation provided here assumes that Eq. (13) represents the RDS, the presented methodology can be extended to other possible RDS scenarios (e.g. $\alpha \approx 1, 1.5, 2, \dots$). In such cases, a different kinetic expression for j (and j_{ex}) would arise, yet the general approach—linking j_{ex} with the k_{RDS} via equilibrium and rate laws—remains valid. A conceptual framework outlining the methodology is provided in Section S5, see SI.

For the sake of clarity, it is good to mention that the data for c_{H^+} and $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ are taken from Table S3. Considering that at 25 °C, c_{O_2} in 0.1 M HClO_4 is $1.18 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ [74], and that c_{O_2} in this solution changes relative to c_{O_2} in pure water [75–77] according to the Sechenov Eq. [78] and Henry's law, c_{O_2} is calculated over the investigated temperature range, see Table S3.

3.4. Evaluation of ORR polarisation curves obtained in 97.6 wt% H_3PO_4 at temperature 120–180 °C

In Section 3.2, applicability of our methodology on ORR activation energy determination was discussed and verified for broadly investigated system of ORR in aqueous HClO_4 (where the ORR mechanism has been widely studied) in context of likely reaction mechanism and reactant concentration. In the next step, this approach was applied to much more complex system of ORR under conditions relevant to HT-PEMFCs. It should be emphasised that investigating ORR under such conditions is experimentally very demanding. As main practical issues can be mentioned problems with electrolyte purity, higher noise levels, the problem of selecting an appropriate reference electrode and accurate determination of its liquid junction potential. This leaves open questions such as what is actual state of Pt surface during ORR, what is extent of phosphate adsorption and how exactly phosphates affects ORR kinetics and mechanism [79] etc. This leads to poor level of ORR mechanism understanding under these conditions and limited availability of material constants in the literature. Still, the methodology was used in order to stress significance of temperature dependence of reacting species concentration on the activation energy evaluation. The measured voltammetry curves are presented in Fig. 4. It can be seen that the j in general raises with increasing temperature.

According to Koutecky-Levich equation (Eq. (10)), the measured current density contains contributions of the kinetic current density j_k and limiting current density j_{lim} . At high overpotentials, the reciprocal value of j_k can be neglected and the relation simplifies to $j \approx j_{\text{lim}}$, which can be expressed using formula known as Levich equation (Eq. (28)),

$$j_{\text{lim}} = 0.62fnFc_{\text{O}_2}D_{\text{O}_2}^{2/3}\omega^{1/2}\nu^{-1/6} \quad (28)$$

where $n = 4$ (considering four-electron reduction of O_2), $f (=1.25)$ is factor accounting for the different geometry of the RRE compared to the RDE [36,80], ω represents angular velocity of rotating electrode, D_{O_2} is diffusion coefficient of O_2 in H_3PO_4 , c_{O_2} is concentration of O_2 dissolved

Fig. 4. ORR polarisation curves at temperatures of 120–180 °C obtained at RRE using revolution rates 2500 rpm; GC electrode, 97.6 wt% H_3PO_4 , 5 mV s^{-1} , corrected for background currents and uncompensated resistance, use of corresponding $E_{\text{ORR,g,T}}$, Hispec4000, 10 $\mu\text{g}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$

Table 2

$c_{\text{O}_2} D_{\text{O}_2}^{2/3}$ values calculated using Levich equation, determined from LSVs obtained at RRE using revolution rates 2500 rpm; GC electrode, 97.6 wt% H_3PO_4 , 5 mV s^{-1} , corrected for background currents and uncompensated resistance, Hispec4000 10 $\mu\text{g}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$, use of corresponding $E_{\text{ORR},g,T}$, “Extrapol.” means that the literature value was not directly measured, but extrapolated by authors of [18,86,87]

$t / ^\circ\text{C}$	$c_{\text{O}_2} D_{\text{O}_2}^{2/3} / 10^{-7}$ $\text{mol s}^{-2/3} \text{m}^{-5/3}$ This work	$D_{\text{O}_2} / 10^{-9}$ $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$ Ref.	$c_{\text{O}_2} / \text{mol m}^{-3}$ Ref.	$c_{\text{O}_2} D_{\text{O}_2}^{2/3} / 10^{-7}$ $\text{mol s}^{-2/3} \text{m}^{-5/3}$ Ref.
120	2.07	2.14 @ 125 °C [18] 0.45 [84]	0.097 @ 125 °C [18] 0.41 [84] 0.31–0.35 [87]	1.61 @ 125 °C [18] 2.41 [84] 1.82–2.06 [87]
140	3.36	No data	No data 0.11 @ 150 °C [18]	No data 2.22 @ 150 °C [18]
160	3.27	2.99 @ 150 °C [18] 0.85 @ 150 °C [84]	0.40 @ 150 °C [84] 0.32–0.37 @ 150 °C [87]	3.59 @ 150 °C [84] 2.87–3.32 @ 150 °C [87]
180	3.46	5.10 [18] extrapol. 0.09 [86] extrapol.	0.11–0.18 [18] extrapol. 0.36 [86] extrapol.	3.26–5.33 [18] extrapol. 3.38 [86] extrapol.

in H_3PO_4 , and ν is kinematic viscosity of H_3PO_4 (values for different temperatures can be found elsewhere [14,18,33,34,81–90]). Using the Levich equation, the product $c_{\text{O}_2} D_{\text{O}_2}^{2/3}$ can be estimated from experimentally determined j_{lim} values. The results are summarised in Table 2. As can be seen, the measured data show a very good agreement with the literature. It is good to point that the literature data for temperature range of 160–180 °C were obtained by extrapolation from values at lower temperatures (by authors of ref. [18, 87]) and experimental results presented in this work support their validity. For further use, the values of c_{O_2} were taken from [91], where the authors use results from [84] in the form of a parametrised equation.

With the knowledge of j and j_{lim} , the values of j_k can then be calculated from Eq. (10). After plotting the decadic logarithms of the j_k values vs overpotential, Tafel plots are obtained, see Fig. 5. The results of Tafel slope fitting, i.e. Tafel slopes (with corresponding charge transfer coefficients α) and exchange current densities j_{ex} are summarised in Table 3.

Fig. 5. Tafel plots of ORR polarisation curves for temperatures of 120–180 °C, LSVs measured at RRE using revolution rates 2500 rpm; GC electrode, 97.6 wt% H_3PO_4 , 5 mV s^{-1} , corrected for background currents and uncompensated resistance, use of corresponding $E_{\text{ORR},g,T}$, Hispec4000, 10 $\mu\text{g}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$

Table 3

Summary of ORR kinetic parameters determined from Tafel plots at temperatures of 120–180 °C, LSVs measured at RRE using revolution rates 2500 rpm; GC electrode, 97.6 wt% H_3PO_4 , 5 mV s^{-1} , corrected for background currents and uncompensated resistance, use of corresponding $E_{\text{ORR},g,T}$, Hispec4000, 10 $\mu\text{g}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$

$t / ^\circ\text{C}$	Tafel slope / mV dec^{-1}	α	$j_{\text{ex}} / \text{mA m}^{-2}$
120	133 ($R^2 = 0.997$)	0.58 ± 0.01	9.6 ± 0.1
140	127 ($R^2 = 0.989$)	0.65 ± 0.01	17.7 ± 0.2
160	120 ($R^2 = 0.994$)	0.72 ± 0.01	22.4 ± 0.2
180	108 ($R^2 = 0.994$)	0.83 ± 0.01	29.3 ± 0.2

It is important to point that the correction for reactant transport in the electrolyte solution using Koutecky-Levich equation (Eq. (10)) allowing calculating j_k is most precise in the potential region, where $j \ll j_{\text{lim}}$. On the other hand, when $j \rightarrow j_{\text{lim}}$, the error of correction becomes unacceptable. As result, Tafel analysis of j_k should ideally be performed in the potential region where $j \ll j_{\text{lim}}$. This was the case of data measured at temperatures of 140 °C, 160 °C, and 180 °C, where the Tafel slope was determined within the ranges of up to 65 %, 52 %, and 60 % of j_{lim} , respectively. Moreover, as shown in Fig. 5, the linear Tafel region at 160 °C and 180 °C could, in principle, be extended to even lower current densities (resulting in a Tafel plot extending for over two decades of a current density). On the other hand, for the voltammogram obtained at 120 °C, it must be acknowledged that the linear Tafel region was identified in the potential range, where current densities were relatively high, reaching 85 % of j_{lim} . This difficulty, was caused by the relatively high effect of background current correction compared to higher temperatures. Nevertheless, the Tafel slope at 120 °C fits to the trend of other data and in general, the obtained data are in agreement with the literature. It can be seen that the Tafel slope decreases with decreasing temperature (this is consistent with [39–43]) and reaches a value of 120 mV dec^{-1} at 160 °C in 97.6 wt% H_3PO_4 , 164 mV dec^{-1} at 136 °C in 85 wt% H_3PO_4 [92], 126 mV dec^{-1} at 150 °C in 103 wt% H_3PO_4 [19], 125 mV dec^{-1} at 150 °C in 98 wt% H_3PO_4 [18], 100 mV dec^{-1} at 160 °C in 99 wt% H_3PO_4 [36] or 120 mV dec^{-1} at 175 °C in 90 wt% H_3PO_4 [28]. Analogously to the measurements in 0.1 M HClO_4 , the values of j_{ex} increase with temperature. If the ΔG^\ddagger were calculated using data at an arbitrarily chosen overpotential, these data would again not lead to good the acquisition of an Arrhenius plot. The reason for this is the strong dependence of c_{O_2} on T , and in this case also on $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ (Table S4

Fig. 6. Arrhenius plot from j_k at various overpotentials (200–500 mV vs. E_{ORR}) at temperatures of 120–180 °C, LSVs measured at RRE using revolution rates 2500 rpm; GC electrode, 97.6 wt% H_3PO_4 , 5 mV s^{-1} , corrected for background currents and uncompensated resistance use of corresponding $E_{\text{ORR},g,T}$, S2, Hispec4000, 10 $\mu\text{g}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$

and Table 2). Similarly to Section 3.2, additional overpotential effects will also occur here. Additionally, for high overpotentials (e.g. 450 and 500 mV), obtained j_k values are strongly affected by the correct determination of j_{lim} (Eq. (10)), which can lead to significant deviations, see Fig. 6.

As discussed in the case of previous measurements in 0.1 M HClO₄, when $\alpha \approx 0.5$, it can be assumed, that the first electron transfer reaction represents a RDS in the whole ORR process. We are aware, that this assumption of $\alpha \approx 0.5$ is little questionable for $\alpha \approx 0.83$, determined for temperature of 180 °C. At the same time, the temperature dependence of α suggests gradual changes in the equilibrium constants or surface coverages (i.e. factors that were assumed to be constant in the above shown derivation, Section 3.3), under the used conditions. Still, the fact that $\alpha < 1$ indicates involvement of the same mechanism and RDS at all temperatures. Nevertheless, even if the RDS were different or, for example, the charge transfer coefficient α were equal to 1, this would not invalidate the general methodology. Rather, it would result in a different functional relationship between the rate constant k and j_{ex} and reactant concentration c_x , i.e., $k = f(j_{\text{ex}}, c_x)$, whose exact form can be derived using suggested procedure. Therefore, the data were used for analysis of the activation energy of ORR. In principle, the same equations (Eq. (25) and Eq. (27)) discussed in Section 3.3 can be used to evaluate the ΔG^\ddagger from the LSVs in high temperature H₃PO₄. However, due to lack of data, it was assumed that $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, representing the molar ratio of H₂O in H₃PO₄, can be approximated by $a_{\text{H}_2\text{O},1}$ (assuming is $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ is proportional to $a_{\text{H}_2\text{O},1}$) as defined by Eq. S6. In addition, the c_{H^+} value was assumed to be constant for the same reason, see Table S4 in SI. The values of c_{O_2} were taken from [91], where the authors use results from [84] in the form of a parametrised equation.

3.5. Activation energy of ORR

The relationships developed in Section 3.3 were used to evaluate ΔG^\ddagger from the dependence of $\ln(\tilde{k}^\circ)$ (with \tilde{k}° being directly proportional to k°) on $1/T$ for ORR in aqueous and H₃PO₄ environment. Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 summarise the Arrhenius plots obtained by using the directly experimentally determined j_{ex} (values uncorrected for the temperature dependence of concentrations of reactants and products) and the above developed procedure (leading to $\tilde{k}^\circ_{\text{as}}$ and $\tilde{k}^\circ_{\text{dis}}$), respectively. In particular, j_{ex} values were determined at equilibrium potentials $E_{\text{ORR},T}$, i.e. these corresponding to given temperature and system composition (5–60 °C 0.1 M HClO₄ or 120–180 °C, 98 wt% H₃PO₄). Following treatment is valid assuming that

1. ORR proceeds via above assumed associative (or dissociative) mechanism,
2. it is possible to consider the condition that RDS of ORR is the electrochemical single-electron reduction (α is around 0.5, true for 0.1 M HClO₄ measurements; questionable for $\alpha \approx 0.83$, i.e. significantly greater than 0.5, at 180 °C in 98 wt% H₃PO₄)
3. the terms K_1 , c_{O_2} , $(E_{\text{ORR}}^\circ - E_2^\circ)/RT$ and $(E_{\text{ORR}}^\circ - E_3^\circ)/RT$ (and c_{H^+} , in the case of 120–180 °C H₃PO₄) do not vary significantly with temperature.

Obtained j_{ex} values were then used to extract corresponding \tilde{k}° values, taking into account system composition (5–60 °C 0.1 M HClO₄ and 120–180 °C, 98 wt% H₃PO₄) and β at each individual temperature for the two different ORR mechanisms.

As can be seen in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8, both, the Arrhenius plots calculated based on experimentally determined j_{ex} values (left y axis) and calculated $\tilde{k}^\circ_{\text{as/dis}}$ values (using Eq. (25) or Eq. (27)) (right y axis) show reasonable linearity. The error of the linear interpolation of $\ln(\tilde{k}^\circ)$ vs. $1/T$ is not significantly different than using the j_{ex} . The resulting $\Delta G^\ddagger_{\text{as}}$ values for associative (+51.9 kJ mol⁻¹, obtained using $\tilde{k}^\circ_{\text{as}}$) and dissociative mechanism $\Delta G^\ddagger_{\text{dis}}$ (+45.0 kJ mol⁻¹, obtained using $\tilde{k}^\circ_{\text{dis}}$) are higher than $\Delta G^\ddagger_{j_{\text{ex}}}$ calculated using j_{ex} (+36.4 kJ mol⁻¹). Considering the previously discussed higher error load in the Tafel slope determination for measurements in H₃PO₄ at 120 °C, an attempt was made to eliminate this value from the determination of G^\ddagger . The results for $\Delta G^\ddagger_{\text{as}}$ and $\Delta G^\ddagger_{\text{dis}}$ are thus 12.99 ± 0.03 kJ mol⁻¹ ($R^2 = 0.997$) and 15.22 ± 0.02 kJ mol⁻¹ ($R^2 = 0.998$), respectively. The difference between $\Delta G^\ddagger_{j_{\text{ex}}}$ value and $\Delta G^\ddagger_{\text{as/dis}}$ is caused by the fact that while $\Delta G^\ddagger_{j_{\text{ex}}}$ is affected by the concentrations of species involved in the ORR, $\Delta G^\ddagger_{\text{as/dis}}$ are free from such effects. In the case of ORR in 0.1 M HClO₄, the most prominent concentration changes occurring are due to variation of O₂ solubility with temperature. Within the observed temperature range of 5–60 °C, c_{O_2} decreases to approximately one-third of its original value. But if the effect of β in Eq. (25) or Eq. (27), is considered, for the term $c_{\text{O}_2}^{1/2-\beta/4}$ and $c_{\text{O}_2}^{1-\beta/4}$ that means decrease by 36 % and 61 %, respectively. In contrast, the term $c_{\text{H}^+}^{1-\beta}$ within the temperature range of 5–60 °C decreases by only approximately 25 %. In other words, concentration effects free ΔG^\ddagger values are about a 42 % ($\Delta G^\ddagger_{\text{as}}$) and 24 % ($\Delta G^\ddagger_{\text{dis}}$) higher. However, it is the j_k value that is normally used in the ΔG^\ddagger calculation, so $\Delta G^\ddagger_{j_k}$ values

Fig. 7. Calculated ΔG^\ddagger with consideration of appropriate $E_{\text{ORR},T}$ and corrections for reaction mechanisms and reactant/product concentrations, determined from LSVs obtained at RDE using revolution rates 900 rpm; Pt electrode, 5–60 °C, 0.1 M HClO₄, 10 mV s⁻¹, corrected for background currents and uncompensated resistance, use of appropriate unit of k° according to the mechanism

Use of	$\Delta G^\ddagger / \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$
j_{ex}	36.4 ± 0.4 ($R^2 = 0.99$)
$\tilde{k}^\circ_{\text{as}}$	51.9 ± 0.6 ($R^2 = 0.99$)
$\tilde{k}^\circ_{\text{dis}}$	45.0 ± 0.6 ($R^2 = 0.99$)

Fig. 8. Calculated ΔG^\ddagger with consideration of appropriate $E_{\text{ORR},g,T}$ and corrections for reaction mechanisms and reactant/product concentrations, determined from LSVs obtained at RRE using revolution rates 2500 rpm; GC electrode, 120–180 °C, 97.6 wt% H_3PO_4 , 5 mV s^{-1} , corrected for background currents and uncompensated resistance, Hispec4000, 10 $\mu\text{g}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$, use of appropriate unit of \tilde{k}° according to the mechanism.

found in the literature for similar conditions are +20 kJ mol^{-1} in 0.1 M HClO_4 (overpotential of 300–400 mV [25], temperature between 25 and 60 °C), +28 kJ mol^{-1} in 0.5 M HClO_4 (overpotential 350 mV [93]), +38 kJ mol^{-1} in 0.1 M HClO_4 , theoretical study [94] or +35–38 kJ mol^{-1} in 0.1 M HClO_4 [52] (overpotential 525–615 mV, temperature 20–90 °C). Upon closer look on the activation energy results from the cited studies, it can be shown, for example, in [25], that the j_k values from Fig. 3 lead to a similar $\Delta G_{j_k}^\ddagger$ (around 18.4 kJ mol^{-1}) value within the temperature range of 25–60 °C and overpotentials of 300–400 mV, or $\Delta G_{j_k}^\ddagger$ around 27.5 kJ mol^{-1} , within the temperature range of 20–60 °C and overpotentials of 500–600 mV (compare with 35 kJ mol^{-1} from [52]). For more on the determination of $\Delta G_{j_k}^\ddagger$ from the j_k values at various overpotential, see Section S6.

One of the main factors influencing the value of ΔG^\ddagger of ORR in H_3PO_4 includes change in $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, which increases by about 70 % in the temperature interval of 120–180 °C. In contrast, the c_{O_2} only increases by about 20 % over the investigated temperature interval. With consideration of β changes in Eq. (25) or Eq. (27), then the term $c_{\text{O}_2}^{1/2-\beta/4}$ increases by 70 % in case of dissociative mechanism (in associative case $c_{\text{O}_2}^{1-\beta/4}$ increases by 85 %) in the temperature range of interest, while the term $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\beta/2}$ decreases only by 20 %. The question is whether the use of Eq. (25) or Eq. (27), which was derived by considering that the reaction mechanism contains only one RDS, which is the first electronation reaction, is correct if the α is already significantly greater than 0.5 at 180 °C (already 0.83). In this case, the value of $\Delta G_{j_{\text{ex}}}^\ddagger$ is, in contrast with HClO_4 measurements, overestimated (since it involves an increase in the concentration of H_2O , the product, rather than a reactant, O_2 , as is the previous case). The resulting $\Delta G_{\text{as}}^\ddagger$ (+16.9 kJ mol^{-1}) value is about a 37 % lower than $\Delta G_{j_{\text{ex}}}^\ddagger$ (+26.7 kJ mol^{-1}), in the case of $\Delta G_{\text{dis}}^\ddagger$ (+19.1 kJ mol^{-1}) is value of about a 29 % lower. ΔG^\ddagger values found in the literature for similar conditions are +66.1 kJ mol^{-1} in 98 wt% H_3PO_4 [18], +54.8 kJ mol^{-1} in 85 wt% H_3PO_4 [92], +41.8 kJ mol^{-1} in 85 wt% H_3PO_4 [95] or +33.1 kJ mol^{-1} in 85 wt% H_3PO_4 [23].

The difference between the value of $\Delta G_{\text{as}}^\ddagger$ and $\Delta G_{\text{dis}}^\ddagger$ (in the temperature range of 5–60 °C difference is about 13 %, in the temperature range of 120–180 °C difference about 12 %) does not seem to be significant. However, if the ORR mechanism is known or, for example, two catalysts with similar composition are compared, the calculation can be based directly on the $\tilde{k}_{\text{dis/as}}^\circ \propto j_{\text{ex}}$ relation for the corresponding ORR

Use of	$\Delta G^\ddagger / \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$
j_{ex}	26.7 ± 1.1 ($R^2 = 0.96$)
$\tilde{k}_{\text{as}}^\circ$	16.9 ± 1.9 ($R^2 = 0.89$)
$\tilde{k}_{\text{dis}}^\circ$	19.1 ± 1.7 ($R^2 = 0.91$)

mechanisms. Conversely, $\Delta G_{j_{\text{ex}}}^\ddagger$ value determined directly from j_{ex} values is overestimated which may lead to incorrect conclusions, cause inconsistencies with other methods of obtaining ΔG^\ddagger , (etc).

Finally, it is interesting to look at Arrhenius plots constructed using j_k values at various overpotentials, as presented in Fig. 3 and Fig. 6 for 0.1 M HClO_4 and 98 wt% H_3PO_4 , respectively. There are several reasons, why the data at individual overpotentials do not follow the Arrhenius equation. First, as discussed above, j_k values depend on concentration of reactants at individual temperatures, particularly, the change in the solubility of O_2 in the electrolyte within the temperature range. For example, the O_2 solubility c_{O_2} decreases by nearly 64 % over the temperature range between 5 °C and 65 °C, see Table S3. This holds true also for the j_{ex} values. In addition to that, at nonzero overpotentials, where ORR occurs at measurable rate, state at the electrode surface can change significantly. This might involve oxidation/reduction of Pt surface, change from equilibrium to steady state conditions which are reflected as, e.g. change in free adsorption site concentration c_\ominus or even their nature.

The ΔG^\ddagger calculated via the proposed methodology can be discussed in the context of currently most often applied methodologies. Currently, a simple analysis of current densities determined at the same (over) potential is usually used to determine the activation energy. The resulting value is referred to as “an apparent” activation energy, yet the physical and chemical interpretation of such a value remains questionable. The methodology developed in this study aims to determine the activation energy for multielectron, multistep reactions, albeit with the limitation that mechanism and RDS remain constant at all temperatures. Obtaining the “true” activation energy of such processes is undoubtedly a complex task; however, the presented work provides a direction believed to be fundamentally correct. The study clearly identifies the parameters needed for ΔG^\ddagger determination. While some of them are not easily available, they could, in principle, be obtained by experiments or theoretical calculations. At present, these unknown parameters were neglected (and considered independent on temperature) and this was explicitly acknowledged. In this way, the ΔG^\ddagger was stripped from the effect of changing reactant/product concentration considering given reaction mechanism and RDS. For example, compared to $\Delta G_{j_{\text{ex}}}^\ddagger$, the correction leads to the higher ΔG^\ddagger value in HClO_4 , and lower ΔG^\ddagger value in H_3PO_4 . Finally, a short note on the physical-chemical meaning of the ΔG^\ddagger value obtained by the above described methodology is required. Since the ΔG^\ddagger value was obtained by extrapolating of j_k using Tafel

equation from certain nonzero overpotentials to equilibrium potential, ΔG^\ddagger does not represent the true ΔG^\ddagger which would be found in the system at equilibrium potential. Instead, it corresponds to ΔG^\ddagger of the reaction on the electrode surface with composition present at overpotentials from which extrapolation was performed. It is important to keep in mind that extrapolation to equilibrium potential is necessary to make ΔG^\ddagger free from overpotential effect (see Section S6, Eq. S29).

4. Conclusion

The primary focus of this work was on the determination of ORR activation energy E^\ddagger from experimentally obtained ORR polarisation curves. Most importantly, it is strictly necessary to consider changes in equilibrium potentials with temperature, E_T . It was also shown, that the often used procedure based on determining E^\ddagger (or in this case ΔG^\ddagger) directly from $j_{k,T}$ at constant overpotential or exchange current densities $j_{ex,T}$ (using correctly determined $E_{ORR,T}$ values) is fundamentally incorrect. First of all, even in the case of elementary electrochemical reaction a nonlinear dependence (influenced by system composition and symmetry factor β) exists between, $j_{ex,T}$ and standard rate constant, k_T° . Moreover, in the case of complex reactions, the particular form of the k_T on $j_{ex,T}$ dependence is influenced also by the reaction mechanism. If this reaction mechanism is known and the RDS (with rate constant $k_{RDS,T}$) is present in the sequence of the elementary steps, an analytical solution in form $k_{RDS,T} = f(j_{ex,T})$ can be obtained. It is also good to point out that the formula, in case of complex reactions, contains (generally temperature dependent) parameters describing pseudo-equilibrium steps prior to and after the RDS. These parameters have to be obtained or estimated.

First, the developed methodology was verified while assessing the activation energy of ORR under LTPM FC-relevant conditions, i.e. in aqueous HClO_4 at temperatures of 5–60 °C. The reason for selecting this system is wide availability of the composition data. In the second step, it was used to determine ΔG^\ddagger under HTPM FC-relevant conditions (i.e. in concentrated H_3PO_4 at temperatures of 120–180 °C), where the information about system composition is somewhat limited. The particular methodology applicable to correct calculation of the standard redox potentials $E_{ORR,T}^\circ$ and consequently $E_{ORR,T}$ depending on various changes of activities of reacting components and temperature was also described. Moreover, the difference between the values of ΔG^\ddagger calculated from \tilde{k}_{as}° and \tilde{k}_{dis}° is, in this particular case, insignificant. On the other hand, the ΔG^\ddagger values for both these mechanisms differ substantially from the ΔG^\ddagger value that would be (though incorrectly) obtained directly from the j_{ex} . Finally, though the above treatment was developed in context of ORR, the approach is, in principal, general and can be applied to any electrochemical reaction.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

J.D. Buriánek: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Data curation. **T. Bystron:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **K. Bouzek:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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References

- [1] A. Bergmann, D. Gerteisen, T. Kurz, Modelling of CO poisoning and its dynamics in HTPM fuel cells, *Fuel Cells* 10 (2) (2010) 278–287.
- [2] M. Prokop, M. Drakselova, K. Bouzek, Review of the experimental study and prediction of Pt-based catalyst degradation during PEM fuel cell operation, *Curr. Opin. Electrochem.* 20 (2020) 20–27.
- [3] J.-H. Wee, Applications of proton exchange membrane fuel cell systems, *Renew. Sust. Energ. Rev.* 11 (8) (2007) 1720–1738.
- [4] C.-Y. Lee, et al., Real-time monitoring of HT-PEMFC, *Membranes* 12 (1) (2022) 94.
- [5] R. Taccani, T. Chinese, M. Boaro, Effect of accelerated ageing tests on PBI HTPM fuel cells performance degradation, *Int. J. Hydrog. Energy* 42 (3) (2017) 1875–1883.
- [6] J. Zhang, et al., Advancement toward polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cells at elevated temperatures, *Research* 2020 (2020).
- [7] L. Qingfeng, H.A. Hjuler, N.J. Bjerrum, Oxygen reduction on carbon supported platinum catalysts in high temperature polymer electrolytes, *Electrochim. Acta* 45 (25–26) (2000) 4219–4226.
- [8] L. Qingfeng, H.A. Hjuler, N. Bjerrum, Phosphoric acid doped polybenzimidazole membranes: physicochemical characterization and fuel cell applications, *J. Appl. Electrochem.* 31 (2001) 773–779.
- [9] M. Rau, et al., Characterization of membrane electrode assemblies for high-temperature PEM fuel cells, *Fuel Cells* 16 (5) (2016) 577–583.
- [10] J. Müller-Hülstede, et al., Towards the reduction of Pt loading in high temperature proton exchange membrane fuel cells—effect of Fe–N–C in Pt-alloy cathodes, *ChemSusChem* 16 (5) (2023) e202202046.
- [11] P. Stonehart, Development of advanced Noble metal-alloy Electrocatalysts for phosphoric acid fuel cells (PAFC), *Ber. Bunsenges. Phys. Chem.* 94 (9) (1990) 913–921.
- [12] H. Lin, et al., High-temperature rotating disk electrode study of platinum bimetallic catalysts in phosphoric acid, *ACS Catal.* 13 (8) (2023) 5635–5642.
- [13] K. Hooshyari, et al., A review of recent developments and advanced applications of high-temperature polymer electrolyte membranes for PEM fuel cells, *Energies* 14 (17) (2021) 5440.
- [14] Z. Liu, et al., Study of the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) at Pt interfaced with phosphoric acid doped polybenzimidazole at elevated temperature and low relative humidity, *Electrochim. Acta* 51 (19) (2006) 3914–3923.
- [15] L. Pavko, et al., Correlating oxygen functionalities and electrochemical durability of carbon supports for electrocatalysts, *Carbon* 215 (2023) 118458.
- [16] H. Xu, et al., Effect of elevated temperature and reduced relative humidity on ORR kinetics for PEM fuel cells, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 152 (9) (2005) A1828.
- [17] A.B. Anderson, et al., Activation energies for oxygen reduction on platinum alloys: theory and experiment, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 109 (3) (2005) 1198–1203.
- [18] B.R. Scharifker, P. Zelenay, J.M. Bockris, The kinetics of oxygen reduction in molten phosphoric acid at high temperatures, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 134 (11) (1987) 2714.
- [19] S. Clouser, J. Huang, E. Yeager, Temperature dependence of the Tafel slope for oxygen reduction on platinum in concentrated phosphoric acid, *J. Appl. Electrochem.* 23 (1993) 597–605.
- [20] J. Zhang, et al., High temperature PEM fuel cells, *J. Power Sources* 160 (2) (2006) 872–891.
- [21] T. Sousa, M. Mamlouk, K. Scott, An isothermal model of a laboratory intermediate temperature fuel cell using PBI doped phosphoric acid membranes, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 65 (8) (2010) 2513–2530.

- [22] T. Sousa, M. Mamlouk, K. Scott, A non-isothermal model of a laboratory intermediate temperature fuel cell using PBI doped phosphoric acid membranes, *Fuel Cells* 10 (6) (2010) 993–1012.
- [23] W. O'Grady, E. Taylor, S. Srinivasan, Electroreduction of oxygen on reduced platinum in 85% phosphoric acid, *J. Electroanal. Chem. Interfacial Electrochem.* 132 (1982) 137–150.
- [24] M. Mamlouk, T. Sousa, K. Scott, A high temperature polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cell model for reformat gas, *Int. J. Electrochem.* 2011 (2011).
- [25] U. Paulus, et al., Oxygen reduction on carbon-supported Pt–Ni and Pt–Co alloy catalysts, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 106 (16) (2002) 4181–4191.
- [26] W. Yuan, et al., Model prediction of effects of operating parameters on proton exchange membrane fuel cell performance, *Renew. Energy* 35 (3) (2010) 656–666.
- [27] E. Romero-Pascual, J. Soler, Modelling of an HTPeM-based micro-combined heat and power fuel cell system with methanol, *Int. J. Hydrog. Energy* 39 (8) (2014) 4053–4059.
- [28] J. McBreen, W. Ogrady, R. Richter, Rotating disk electrode apparatus for the study of fuel cell reactions at elevated temperatures and pressures, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* (1984) 131 (United States).
- [29] Y. Li, et al., Influence of phosphoric anions on oxygen reduction reaction activity of platinum, and strategies to inhibit phosphoric anion adsorption, *Chin. J. Catal.* 37 (7) (2016) 1134–1141.
- [30] B.F. Gomes, et al., Effect of phosphoric acid purity on the electrochemically active surface area of Pt-based electrodes, *J. Electroanal. Chem.* 918 (2022) 116450.
- [31] N. Sugishima, J.T. Hinatsu, F.R. Foulkes, Phosphorous acid impurities in phosphoric acid fuel cell electrolytes: I. Voltammetric study of impurity formation, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 141 (12) (1994) 3325.
- [32] M. Prokop, et al., H₃PO₃ electrochemical behaviour on a bulk Pt electrode: adsorption and oxidation kinetics, *Electrochim. Acta* 212 (2016) 465–472.
- [33] D.I. MacDonald, J.R. Boyack, Density, electrical conductivity, and vapor pressure of concentrated phosphoric acid, *J. Chem. Eng. Data* 14 (3) (1969) 380–384.
- [34] X. Jiang, et al., Density, viscosity, and thermal conductivity of electronic grade phosphoric acid, *J. Chem. Eng. Data* 56 (2) (2011) 205–211.
- [35] M. Prokop, et al., A rotating rod electrode disk as an alternative to the rotating disk electrode for medium-temperature electrolytes, part I: the effect of the absence of cylindrical insulation, *Electrochim. Acta* 245 (2017) 634–642.
- [36] M. Prokop, et al., A rotating rod electrode disk as an alternative to the rotating disk electrode for medium-temperature electrolytes, part II: an example of the application in an investigation of the oxygen reduction reaction on a Pt/C catalyst by the thin film method in hot concentrated H₃PO₄, *Electrochim. Acta* 245 (2017) 597–606.
- [37] W. Wagner, A. Pruß, The IAPWS formulation 1995 for the thermodynamic properties of ordinary water substance for general and scientific use, *J. Phys. Chem. Ref. Data Monogr.* 31 (2) (2002) 387–535.
- [38] J.K. Nørskov, et al., Origin of the overpotential for oxygen reduction at a fuel-cell cathode, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 108 (46) (2004) 17886–17892.
- [39] A. Damjanovic, D. Sepa, An analysis of the pH dependence of enthalpies and Gibbs energies of activation for O₂ reduction at Pt electrodes in acid solutions, *Electrochim. Acta* 35 (7) (1990) 1157–1162.
- [40] D. Sepa, et al., Apparent enthalpies of activation of electrodic oxygen reduction at platinum in different current density regions—I, *Electrochimica Acta* 31 (1) (1986) 91–96.
- [41] D. Sepa, et al., Different views regarding the kinetics and mechanisms of oxygen reduction at Pt and Pd electrodes, *Electrochim. Acta* 32 (1) (1987) 129–134.
- [42] D. Sepa, M. Vojnovic, A. Damjanovic, Reaction intermediates as a controlling factor in the kinetics and mechanism of oxygen reduction at platinum electrodes, *Electrochim. Acta* 26 (6) (1981) 781–793.
- [43] D. Sepa, et al., Symmetry factor and transfer coefficient in analysis of enthalpies of activation and mechanisms of oxygen reduction at platinum electrodes, *Electrochim. Acta* 31 (11) (1986) 1401–1402.
- [44] J. Wang, N. Markovic, R. Adzic, Kinetic analysis of oxygen reduction on Pt (111) in acid solutions: intrinsic kinetic parameters and anion adsorption effects, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 108 (13) (2004) 4127–4133.
- [45] T. Shinagawa, A.T. Garcia-Esparza, K. Takanabe, Insight on Tafel slopes from a microkinetic analysis of aqueous electrocatalysis for energy conversion, *Sci. Rep.* 5 (1) (2015) 13801.
- [46] A. Holewinski, S. Linic, Elementary mechanisms in electrocatalysis: revisiting the ORR Tafel slope, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 159 (11) (2012) H864.
- [47] L. Ou, S. Chen, Comparative study of oxygen reduction reaction mechanisms on the Pd (111) and Pt (111) surfaces in acid medium by DFT, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 117 (3) (2013) 1342–1349.
- [48] J. Greeley, et al., Alloys of platinum and early transition metals as oxygen reduction electrocatalysts, *Nat. Chem.* 1 (7) (2009) 552–556.
- [49] J. Greeley, J.K. Nørskov, A general scheme for the estimation of oxygen binding energies on binary transition metal surface alloys, *Surf. Sci.* 592 (1–3) (2005) 104–111.
- [50] G. Shi, et al., Temperature dependence of oxygen reduction activity at Pt/Nb-doped SnO₂ catalysts with varied Pt loading, *ACS Catal.* 11 (9) (2021) 5222–5230.
- [51] N. Wakabayashi, et al., Temperature dependence of oxygen reduction activity at Pt–Fe, Pt–Co, and Pt–Ni alloy electrodes, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 109 (12) (2005) 5836–5841.
- [52] N. Wakabayashi, et al., Temperature-dependence of oxygen reduction activity at a platinum electrode in an acidic electrolyte solution investigated with a channel flow double electrode, *J. Electroanal. Chem.* 574 (2) (2005) 339–346.
- [53] Z. Duan, G. Wang, A first principles study of oxygen reduction reaction on a Pt (111) surface modified by a subsurface transition metal M (M = Ni, Co, or Fe), *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 13 (45) (2011) 20178–20187.
- [54] A. Savara, Standard states for adsorption on solid surfaces: 2D gases, surface liquids, and Langmuir adsorbates, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 117 (30) (2013) 15710–15715.
- [55] A.M. Gómez-Marín, J.M. Feliu, New insights into the oxygen reduction reaction mechanism on Pt (111): a detailed electrochemical study, *ChemSusChem* 6 (6) (2013) 1091–1100.
- [56] A.M. Gómez-Marín, R. Rizo, J.M. Feliu, Oxygen reduction reaction at Pt single crystals: a critical overview, *Catal. Sci. Technol.* 4 (6) (2014) 1685–1698.
- [57] M.J. Janik, C.D. Taylor, M. Neurock, First-principles analysis of the initial electroreduction steps of oxygen over Pt (111), *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 156 (1) (2008) B126.
- [58] T. Jacob, B.V. Merinov, W.A. Goddard III, Chemisorption of atomic oxygen on Pt (111) and Pt/Ni (1 1 1) surfaces, *Chem. Phys. Lett.* 385 (5–6) (2004) 374–377.
- [59] T. Jacob, R.P. Muller, W.A. Goddard, Chemisorption of atomic oxygen on Pt (111) from DFT studies of Pt-clusters, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 107 (35) (2003) 9465–9476.
- [60] T. Jacob, The mechanism of forming H₂O from H₂ and O₂ over a Pt catalyst via direct oxygen reduction, *Fuel Cells* 6 (3–4) (2006) 159–181.
- [61] T. Jacob, W.A. Goddard III, Water formation on Pt and Pt-based alloys: a theoretical description of a catalytic reaction, *ChemPhysChem* 7 (5) (2006) 992–1005.
- [62] J. Zhang, et al., Controlling the catalytic activity of platinum-monolayer electrocatalysts for oxygen reduction with different substrates, *Angew. Chem.* 117 (14) (2005) 2170–2173.
- [63] J. Zhang, et al., Mixed-metal Pt monolayer electrocatalysts for enhanced oxygen reduction kinetics, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 127 (36) (2005) 12480–12481.
- [64] V. Tripkovic, T. Vegge, Potential-and rate-determining step for oxygen reduction on Pt (111), *J. Phys. Chem. C* 121 (48) (2017) 26785–26793.
- [65] A. Tegou, et al., A rotating disc electrode study of oxygen reduction at platinumized nickel and cobalt coatings, *J. Solid State Electrochem.* 14 (2010) 175–184.
- [66] J. Gland, V. Korchak, The adsorption of oxygen on a stepped platinum single crystal surface, *Surf. Sci.* 75 (4) (1978) 733–750.
- [67] J.L. Gland, Molecular and atomic adsorption of oxygen on the Pt (111) and Pt (S)-12 (111)×(111) surfaces, *Surf. Sci.* 93 (2–3) (1980) 487–514.
- [68] J.L. Gland, B.A. Sexton, G.B. Fisher, Oxygen interactions with the Pt (111) surface, *Surf. Sci.* 95 (2–3) (1980) 587–602.
- [69] A. Eichler, J. Hafner, Molecular precursors in the dissociative adsorption of O₂ on Pt (111), *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 79 (22) (1997) 4481.
- [70] C. Campbell, et al., A molecular beam study of the catalytic oxidation of CO on a Pt (111) surface, *J. Chem. Phys.* 73 (11) (1980) 5862–5873.
- [71] N. Marković, P. Ross Jr., Surface science studies of model fuel cell electrocatalysts, *Surf. Sci. Rep.* 45 (4–6) (2002) 117–229.
- [72] M. Chatenet, et al., Oxygen reduction on silver catalysts in solutions containing various concentrations of sodium hydroxide—comparison with platinum, *J. Appl. Electrochem.* 32 (10) (2002) 1131–1140.
- [73] B. Grgur, N. Marković, P. Ross, Temperature-dependent oxygen electrochemistry on platinum low-index single crystal surfaces in acid solutions, *Can. J. Chem.* 75 (11) (1997) 1465–1471.
- [74] Y.-C. Wei, C.-W. Liu, K.-W. Wang, Improvement of oxygen reduction reaction and methanol tolerance characteristics for PdCo electrocatalysts by Au alloying and CO treatment, *Chem. Commun.* 47 (43) (2011) 11927–11929.
- [75] G. Ming, D. Zhenhao, Prediction of oxygen solubility in pure water and brines up to high temperatures and pressures, *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* 74 (19) (2010) 5631–5640.
- [76] A.S. Groisman, N.E. Khomutov, Solubility of oxygen in electrolyte solutions, *Russ. Chem. Rev.* 59 (8) (1990) 707.
- [77] B.B. Benson, D. Krause Jr., M.A. Peterson, The solubility and isotopic fractionation of gases in dilute aqueous solution. I. Oxygen, *J. Solut. Chem.* 8 (9) (1979) 655–690.
- [78] A. Schumpe, I. Adler, W.D. Deckwer, Solubility of oxygen in electrolyte solutions, *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* 20 (1) (1978) 145–150.
- [79] A. Kamat, et al., Experimental investigations into phosphoric acid adsorption on platinum catalysts in a high temperature PEM fuel cell, *Fuel Cells* 11 (4) (2011) 511–517.
- [80] M. Prokop, et al., Degradation kinetics of Pt during high-temperature PEM fuel cell operation part I: kinetics of Pt surface oxidation and dissolution in concentrated H₃PO₄ electrolyte at elevated temperatures, *Electrochim. Acta* 313 (2019) 352–366.
- [81] R. Jameson, 151. The composition of the “strong” phosphoric acids, *J. Chem. Soc. (Resumed)* (1959) 752–759.
- [82] K. Schrödter, et al., Phosphoric Acid and Phosphates, *Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry*, 2000.
- [83] F. Gan, D.-T. Chin, Determination of diffusivity and solubility of oxygen in phosphoric acid using a transit time on a rotating ring-disc electrode, *J. Appl. Electrochem.* 23 (5) (1993) 452–455.
- [84] K. Klinedinst, et al., Oxygen solubility and diffusivity in hot concentrated H₃PO₄, *J. Electroanal. Chem. Interfacial Electrochem.* 57 (3) (1974) 281–289.
- [85] R. Mesmer, C. Baes, Phosphoric acid dissociation equilibria in aqueous solutions to 300 C, *J. Solut. Chem.* 3 (1974) 307–322.
- [86] P. Zelenay, et al., A comparison of the properties of CF₃SO₃H and H₃PO₄ in relation to fuel cells, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 133 (11) (1986) 2262.
- [87] K.E. Gubbins, R. Walker, Solubility and diffusivity of hydrocarbons and oxygen in fuel cell electrolytes, *Engineering and Industrial Experiment Station, College of Engineering, University of Florida*, 1965. Contract Number DA-49-186-AMC-45 (X).
- [88] M. Fleige, et al., Evaluation of temperature and electrolyte concentration dependent oxygen solubility and diffusivity in phosphoric acid, *Electrochim. Acta* 209 (2016) 399–406.

- [89] A.-L. Huhti, P.A. Gartaganis, The composition of the strong phosphoric acids, *Can. J. Chem.* 34 (6) (1956) 785–797.
- [90] R. Bhardwaj, M. Enayetullah, J.M. Bockris, Proton activities in concentrated phosphoric and trifluoromethane sulfonic acid at elevated temperature in relation to acid fuel cells, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 137 (7) (1990) 2070.
- [91] D.F. Cheddíe, N.D. Munroe, A two-phase model of an intermediate temperature PEM fuel cell, *Int. J. Hydrog. Energy* 32 (7) (2007) 832–841.
- [92] A. Appleby, Evolution and reduction of oxygen on oxidized platinum in 85% orthophosphoric acid, *J. Electroanal. Chem. Interfacial Electrochem.* 24 (1) (1970) 97–117.
- [93] U. Paulus, et al., Oxygen reduction on a high-surface area Pt/Vulcan carbon catalyst: a thin-film rotating ring-disk electrode study, *J. Electroanal. Chem.* 495 (2) (2001) 134–145.
- [94] J.X. Wang, J. Zhang, R.R. Adzic, Double-trap kinetic equation for the oxygen reduction reaction on Pt (111) in acidic media, *Chem. Eur. J.* 111 (49) (2007) 12702–12710.
- [95] J. Huang, R. Sen, E. Yeager, Oxygen reduction on platinum in 85% orthophosphoric acid, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 126 (5) (1979) 786.